

MIGRATION AND THE INFORMAL LABOUR ECONOMY: A STUDY OF MIGRANT WORKERS IN DELHI

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the link between internal migration and Delhi's informal labour economy through a mixed-methods approach. Surveying migrant households and conducting interviews, the research highlights that migrants—mostly young, low-educated workers—are concentrated in precarious jobs lacking contracts, welfare access, and secure housing. Findings show widespread vulnerabilities, including low wages, poor living conditions, and intensified hardships during COVID-19. The study further reveals the systemic exclusion of migrants from urban planning and welfare frameworks, underscoring the gap between Delhi's current development model and the goals of inclusive, sustainable urbanization under SDG 11. Policy recommendations stress the need for migrant-inclusive social protection, affordable housing, and labour rights.

Key words: Internal Migration, Informal Economy, Urban Vulnerability

1. INTRODUCTION

The International Organisation for Migration defines it as "Persons moving away from their customary residence, either over an international border or within a single country" (IOM Key glossary). The Census of India defined migration in two types one based on birthplace, "When a person is enumerated in Census at a location other than her or his birthplaces, such as a hamlet or town, she or he is deemed a migrant by birthplace" (Census of India 2011). And one based on the place of the last residence as, "If a person's last residence was somewhere other than where he or she was enumerated, that individual would be termed a migrant by place of the last habitation. This approach would provide a better view of the current migration scenario by recording the most recent migrations in cases when people have migrated many times" (Census of India).

Another Important definition as used and defined by NSSO (National Sample Survey Organisation) is *'the one who has a more or less permanent settlement in the place of enumeration, regardless of whether he or she has any contact with the native place, is treated as a permanent immigrant, i.e., both the conditions of permanently leaving the native place and permanently residing in the place of enumeration must be met for a person to be a permanent immigrant'* (NSSO).

1.1 Migration and its types

Migration can be broadly divided into various types based on borders, movements, size, and intentions as discussed (see Table 1.1)

Table 1: Migration and its various Types

Migration Type	Details
1. Migration by Borders	National/internal migration- Intra state, inter-district, inter-state, intra district migration- Rural-rural, Rural-Urban, Urban-urban and Urban-rural International migration
2. Migration by Movement	Circular migration, return migration, counter-stream migration, step migration, chain migration
3. Migration by Size	Individual migration, group migration
4. Migration by Intention	Voluntary migration, involuntary migration

Source: Compiled from various sources

The patterns of migration are complicated. Rural-Urban migration is the most important sort of movement in terms of long-term development, although there is also a lot of R-R, U-U, and even U-R migration. R-U migration is particularly relevant because, even though urban fertility is much lower, the population share of cities is expanding, and R-U migration accounts for the gap. It's also essential because of the potential benefits of city economic activity for development, thanks to agglomeration economies and other variables. However, it is vital to understand urban-rural migration since it frequently occurs when hard times in cities coincide with increases in output prices from the country's cash crops, as happened in most of the developing countries.

1.2 Causes and consequences of Migration

Migration is a complex socio-economic phenomenon shaped by multiple **push and pull factors** that influence people's decision to move from one place to another. **Push factors** are those **adverse conditions at the place of origin** that compel individuals to leave, while **pull factors** refer to the **favorable conditions** at the destination that attract migrants. Both sets of factors operate simultaneously and often overlap, making migration a multi-dimensional process.

Push factors can broadly be categorized *into economic, political, and socio-cultural dimensions*. *Economic and demographic push factors* are among the most prominent. These include *unemployment, low wages, poverty, and the lack of access to basic services such as healthcare, education, housing, and infrastructure*. In contrast, *pull factors* are those *positive elements* at the place of destination that make migration attractive. Economic and demographic pull factors typically include better *employment opportunities, higher wages, and overall improved living standards*. The presence of developed cities with accessible amenities—such as *modern healthcare, education, and housing*—acts as a major magnet for rural and small-town populations. Taken together, push and pull factors provide a comprehensive framework for understanding migration. *While push factors highlight the challenges and deficiencies of the source regions*, pull factors underline the *opportunities and advantages of the destination*. The interplay of these forces explains the persistent patterns of rural-to-urban migration within countries like India, as well as international migration across borders. For policymakers, recognizing these underlying causes is essential for designing strategies that reduce distress migration by improving local development, while also managing the pressures faced by destination regions.

Figure 1: Causes and Consequences of Migration

Source: Lee, E. (1966). A Theory of Migration. *Demography*, 3(1), 47-57. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2060063>.

The social consequences of migration are important. Migrants act as carriers of innovation and change, transferring knowledge of new technologies, family planning practices, and educational opportunities—particularly for women—back to their places of origin. Migration also fosters cultural intermixing, which contributes to the evolution of a composite culture, greater tolerance, and a broadening of people’s intellectual horizons. However, the process is not without drawbacks, as many migrants experience social isolation, anonymity, and alienation in unfamiliar urban environments, leading to a sense of dislocation and psychological stress.

1.3 Internal Migration in India

India's economy is growing at a significant pace, as is its population. We have 17.7 percent of the world's population, and human mobility is required for efficient population relocation. As said, migration is an important livelihood activity (Mosse et al., 2002), and with more transportation and communication facilities, migration within the country has become easier and a part of the process of urbanization and industrialization (Ansari, 2016). There are almost **454 million (45 crores) internal migrants in India**, and they have been gradually increasing in every census count (Government of India, 2017). **India accounts for one-fourth of the fastest-growing cities in the world** (World Economic Forum, 2018). Mumbai, Delhi, and Kolkata have the most populous urban areas in the country, and rural-urban migration happens to be one of the reasons for this (WEF, 2017). According to a recent economic analysis, India's interstate migration rate more than doubled between 2001 and 2011, expanding at a pace of 4.5 per cent per year. The country's annual interstate migration totals around 6 million migrants each year. And it shows the Census count for internal migration with a whopping number of 450 million (Registrar General of India, 2011), an increase of 40% over the previous count for the year 2001.

Figure 2: Percentage of Internal Migrants

Source: Generated Using Data from Periodic Labour Force Survey 2021

1.4 Internal Migration in NCT of Delhi

India is one of the world's fastest-expanding economies, and the National Capital Territory of Delhi is one of the world's megacities, ranking second below Tokyo (World Urbanization Prospects, 2018). Delhi's estimated population in 2018 was 18.5 million (around 2.1 per cent of India's population) and is expected to rise to 38.94 million by 2030 (due to an 81.4% population growth rate). About 65 per cent of India's impoverished live in states like Bihar, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, and Orissa from these states people seeking a better life are flocking to cities like Delhi, which currently has an influx of 8 million in-migrants. According to the Economic Survey of India for 2016-17, Delhi received the most of the inflows. The average net flow of internal migrants at the State Level is shown in Figure 1.5 and the largest recipient of in-migration was Delhi, which accounted for more than half of total in-migration for the year 2015-2016 while U.P. and Bihar have taken together covers almost half of the out-migrants. The top 10 movement streams are estimated to be as follows: UP to Delhi, Bihar to Delhi, UP to Maharashtra, Bihar to West Bengal, Tamil Nadu to Kerala, Bihar to UP, Haryana to Delhi, UP to Gujarat, and Andhra to Karnataka (IIHS, 2011).

1.5 Statement of the problem

The problem statement highlights the dual role of migrants in urban spaces like the National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi: on one hand, they contribute significantly to the city's economic growth, especially through their presence in the informal labour market; on the other, they themselves struggle to access basic amenities and live in precarious, marginalized conditions. This duality reflects a paradox central to urban development in India—while migrants sustain urban economies, their integration into city life remains limited and unsustainable.

The study identifies key gaps in the existing literature and policy debates. First, it points out that although internal migration is a longstanding phenomenon in Delhi, there is inadequate updated research on migrants' living conditions. The ground realities are highly dynamic due to rapid urbanization, changing labour market structures, and shifting socio-political contexts. Second, it raises the critical issue of inclusivity in urban planning. The fact that most migrants are concentrated in informal jobs and slum settlements questions whether the city administration is adopting an inclusive model of urban development or simply exploiting migrant labour without ensuring basic welfare. Third, the problem statement situates the research within the broader discourse of sustainable development by linking it to *Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11*, which emphasizes inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities.

The problem is not only contemporary but also forward-looking. It acknowledges that urbanization cannot realistically be “stopped,” but rather, the challenge is to harness migrant labour productively and inclusively. It also emphasizes the need to examine whether Delhi's

current development trajectory aligns with international standards of sustainability and inclusivity, thereby broadening the study's significance beyond local concerns.

1.6 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are as follows.

1. To study the *internal migrant's contribution towards their development* as well as that of the National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi.
2. To study the *living conditions of internal migrants*, including Covid-19-related experiences, in the NCT of Delhi and issues faced by them while they pursue a way of sustenance.
3. To analyse the *urban conditions in the NCT of Delhi and thereby identify the challenges in achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of 'Sustainable Cities and Communities'*

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of literature has been divided mainly into 4 categories, i.e. *studies on migrant workers, migration in Delhi, informal labour economy and effect of covid-19 on migrants*.

2.1 Studies on Migrant workers

Migration has historically been a defining characteristic of social, economic, and demographic change across nations. In the global South, particularly in rapidly urbanizing economies such as India, the migration of workers from rural to urban areas has become one of the central drivers of city growth and economic transformation (Skeldon, 2021). The economic logic of migration has often been explained through the dual-sector model of development, wherein surplus rural labour shifts to urban industrial or service sectors, thereby fueling urban expansion (Todaro, 1969; Lewis, 1954). Yet, in practice, migrants in cities are often absorbed not into the formal economy but into the burgeoning informal sector, where precarious work, low wages, and limited social protection dominate (Chen, 2020).

The National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi exemplifies this paradox. As India's largest urban agglomeration and a key economic hub, Delhi attracts millions of internal migrants annually (Kundu, 2020). Migrants are vital to sustaining the city's construction, service, domestic, and small-scale industrial sectors. However, their livelihoods remain precarious, characterized by exclusion from housing, health, and welfare services. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020–2021 *exposed the systemic vulnerabilities of migrant workers* when millions were stranded, unemployed, and forced to return to rural homes (Deshingkar, 2022).

Given this context, the present study situates itself at the intersection of migration, informal labour, and urban development in Delhi. To clarify the research problem, this review is structured into four categories: (1) studies on migrant workers, (2) migration in Delhi, (3) the informal labour economy, and (4) COVID-19 and its impact. This first section examines the global and Indian literature on migrant workers, highlighting their contributions, vulnerabilities, and lived experiences.

2.2 Global Perspectives

The literature on migrant workers has expanded considerably, reflecting the centrality of labour migration in globalization. Castles, de Haas, and Miller (2020) note that migration increasingly functions as both a response to economic inequality and a mechanism that sustains global capitalism. Migrant labour fills structural gaps in urban labour markets—such as *low-paid, insecure, and physically demanding jobs that local populations are less willing to undertake* (ILO, 2021). At the same time, migrants remain excluded from social protection, facing heightened risks of exploitation, unsafe working conditions, and discrimination (Anderson, 2010).

From a rights-based perspective, Standing (2011) identifies migrant workers as part of the “precariat,” a social class defined by insecure labour, unstable income, and *lack of collective bargaining power*. This framework resonates strongly with the experiences of migrant workers in developing countries, where informality dominates. Empirical studies in Southeast Asia, Latin America, and Africa demonstrate common patterns of exclusion from formal employment, denial of social security, and concentration in hazardous occupations (Parrenas, 2015; Crush & Tawodzera, 2017).

Recent scholarship emphasizes the intersectionality of migrant labour. Women migrants, for instance, are disproportionately concentrated in domestic and care work, sectors that are undervalued and often excluded from labour regulation (Razavi, 2020). Similarly, caste, ethnicity, and minority status influence access to jobs, wages, and urban citizenship (Nesbitt-Ahmed, 2017). These global insights inform our understanding of migrant workers in India, especially in Delhi, where caste, class, and gender converge in shaping labour market experiences.

2.3 Studies on Migrant Workers in India

India has one of the largest populations of internal migrants globally, with over 450 million people classified as migrants by the Census 2011 (Bhagat & Mohanty, 2019). Economic drivers dominate migration flows, with seasonal and circular migration particularly common among poorer rural households (Deshingkar & Akter, 2009). Migrant workers constitute a critical segment of India’s informal economy, contributing to construction, textiles, domestic service, small-scale manufacturing, and street vending.

Yet, their working conditions are precarious. Studies reveal chronic *issues of low wages, lack of written contracts, absence of occupational safety measures, and exclusion from labour laws* (Srivastava, 2020). Migrants often face “double exclusion”: marginalized in their rural home states due to poverty and limited opportunities, and marginalized again in cities due to their informal, non-citizen-like status (Shah & Lerche, 2020). Migrants from states such as Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand, and West Bengal dominate Delhi’s informal labour supply, yet they often face social stigma, harassment, and exclusion from welfare schemes (Keshri & Bhagat, 2013).

Gender dimensions are equally significant. Women migrants, though undercounted in statistics, form a large proportion of the urban informal workforce, especially in domestic work, garment industries, and waste-picking (Banerjee, 2021). Despite their economic contributions, ***they are subjected to long working hours, gender-based violence, and wage discrimination.*** Studies also note that family migration often leads to informal settlements in slums, ***where access to clean water, sanitation, and healthcare remains inadequate*** (Priya et al., 2018).

Several studies have highlighted the literature consistently highlights *the poor living conditions of migrant workers in cities*. Studies in Delhi, Mumbai, and Bangalore show that migrants predominantly ***reside in slums, unauthorized colonies, or employer-provided temporary shelters near worksites*** (Kundu, 2020). These settlements often ***lack clean water, sanitation, drainage, electricity, and waste management, exposing migrants to health risks***. The absence of legal tenure exacerbates their vulnerability, making them prone to evictions (Dupont, 2019).

Healthcare access is also limited. Migrants are often excluded from urban health programs due to lack of documentation, linguistic barriers, and discrimination (Gupta & Mishra, 2019). Educational opportunities for children of migrants are disrupted by ***frequent mobility, inadequate schooling infrastructure in slums, and exclusion from state services***. These factors reinforce intergenerational cycles of vulnerability.

Many studies have highlighted the exclusion of migrants from welfare and social protection. Welfare schemes in India are primarily domicile-based, linking entitlements to place of origin rather than place of work. Consequently, migrants in Delhi often lack access to subsidized food through the Public Distribution System (PDS), healthcare, housing schemes, or education subsidies (Bhagat & Mohanty, 2019). Though portability of benefits has improved under the “One Nation, One Ration Card” scheme, implementation gaps remain (Agarwal, 2021).

Studies also show that migrants are underrepresented in trade unions and labour organizations, limiting their bargaining power. Their insecure and transient status makes it difficult to organize collectively (Shah & Lerche, 2020). Informal sector employers exploit this gap, reinforcing a cycle of low wages and precarious livelihoods.

Table 2: Various Indicators Showing Latest Data on Migration

Indicator	2011 Census	2023–24
Total internal migrants (Crore)	45.57	40.20
Internal migration rate (%)	37.8	28.9
Intra-state migration share (%)	83.1	88.0
Female migration rate (%)	44.6	47.9
Male migration rate (%)	10.7	10.7

Sources : Created by author by compiling data from Economic Advisory Council -PM Working Papers "400 Million Dreams!" report (2024) and Ministry of Statistics and Program Implementation Migration Report (2023)

Figure 3: Rural Vs Urban Migration

Source: Generated Using Data from Periodic Labour Force Survey 2021

2.4 Migration in Delhi

Delhi, as India's capital and one of the fastest-growing urban agglomerations, has historically been a magnet for internal migration. Its position as the political, administrative, and commercial hub has attracted waves of *rural-to-urban migrants seeking employment, education, and better living standards* (Kundu, 2020). According to Census 2011, Delhi had one of the highest proportions of migrant population among Indian cities, with nearly 45% of its residents born outside the National Capital Territory (NCT) (Bhagat, 2017). Post-2011 estimates suggest this share has only grown, especially due to inflows from economically lagging states such as Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Rajasthan, and West Bengal (Tumbe, 2018).

Migration into Delhi is driven by *both push and pull factors*. On the push side, agrarian distress, lack of rural employment, and socio-political marginalization compel rural households to send

workers to cities (Deshingkar, 2022). On the pull side, Delhi's concentration of industries, services, and construction opportunities acts as a magnet. However, as multiple studies highlight, the "Delhi dream" is highly stratified—while educated, middle-class migrants find opportunities in the formal and white-collar economy, poor rural migrants are absorbed disproportionately into the informal sector (Srivastava, 2020).

Recent NSSO and PLFS data confirm that the majority of migrant workers in Delhi are employed in *casual labour, daily wage work, or self-employment in small-scale enterprises* (NITI Aayog, 2021). The construction industry alone employs lakhs of seasonal migrants, while others are concentrated in *street vending, domestic service, small manufacturing workshops, waste-picking, and transportation* (Keshri & Bhagat, 2013). Importantly, a significant proportion of this labour is circular, with migrants maintaining ties to their villages and returning seasonally for agricultural work or social obligations (Srivastava & Sutradhar, 2016).

Delhi's migrant population is demographically diverse but marked by socio-economic vulnerabilities. Migrants predominantly belong to lower castes, scheduled tribes, and backward classes, which shapes their access to jobs and housing (Shah & Lerche, 2020). Many are first-generation migrants with limited educational attainment, restricting them to low-paying occupations. Women migrants, particularly from Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh, are highly visible *in domestic work, garment factories, and waste collection* (Banerjee, 2021).

Studies also show a strong youth component in migration flows. Keshri and Bhagat (2013) found that migrants aged 15–35 constitute the majority, reflecting both the "youth bulge" in source states and the demand for physically intensive labour in Delhi. This age selectivity has significant implications for urban development, as it reinforces informal employment structures while leaving the rural elderly and children dependent on remittances.

One of the defining features of migration in Delhi is *the concentration of migrants in slums, unauthorized colonies, and peri-urban settlements*. Kundu (2020) documents how migrant workers often live in *rented rooms in overcrowded informal settlements* such as *Seelampur, Sangam Vihar, and parts of East Delhi*. These settlements *lack basic services such as clean water, sanitation, and waste disposal, leading to public health challenges* (Dupont, 2019).

The absence of affordable formal housing options forces migrants into informal rental markets, where landlords exploit their insecure legal status (Priya et al., 2018). *Many construction workers live in temporary shelters at worksites, often with no access to toilets or drinking water*. The housing insecurity contributes to frequent evictions, particularly during urban redevelopment drives, further marginalizing migrant populations (Desai, 2021).

2.5 Migration and Urban Development in Delhi

The integration of migrants into Delhi's urban fabric is paradoxical. On one hand, migrants are indispensable to the functioning of the city—providing cheap labour for construction, transport, domestic service, and informal markets. On the other hand, policy discourse often portrays them as contributors to slum proliferation, congestion, and strain on urban infrastructure (Bhagat & Mohanty, 2019).

Urban planning in Delhi has often failed to recognize migrants as legitimate city dwellers. The Master Plan of Delhi (MPD) largely emphasizes middle-class housing, infrastructure, and beautification, with limited provisions for affordable housing or labour welfare (Bhan, 2016). Consequently, migrants remain excluded from urban citizenship, lacking secure tenure, documentation, and political representation. This exclusion reinforces the precarity of their livelihoods in the informal economy.

Table 3: Trends Of Migration In Delhi 2003-2020

S. No.	Year	*Estimated Mid-Year Population	Increased Population Over Previous Year	Total		Natural Increase	Migration
				Birth	Death		
1.	2003	144.86	2.76	3.01	0.88	2.13	0.63
2.	2004	147.68	2.82	3.06	0.85	2.21	0.61
3.	2005	150.54	2.86	3.24	0.94	2.30	0.56
4.	2006	153.47	2.93	3.23	0.99	2.24	0.69
5.	2007	156.45	2.98	3.22	1.01	2.21	0.77
6.	2008	159.49	3.04	3.34	1.08	2.26	0.78
7.	2009	162.58	3.09	3.54	1.12	2.42	0.67
8.	2010	165.74	3.16	3.59	1.24	2.35	0.81
9.	2011	169.14	3.40	3.53	1.12	2.41	0.99
10.	2012	172.92	3.78	3.60	1.05	2.55	1.23
11.	2013	176.70	3.78	3.70	0.97	2.73	1.05
12.	2014	180.47	3.77	3.74	1.21	2.53	1.24
13.	2015	184.25	3.78	3.74	1.25	2.49	1.29
14.	2016	188.03	3.78	3.79	1.42	2.37	1.41
15.	2017	191.82	3.79	3.67	1.36	2.31	1.48
16.	2018	195.61	3.79	3.63	1.46	2.17	1.62
17.	2019	199.40	3.79	3.66	1.45	2.21	1.58
18.	2020	203.19	3.79	3.02	1.43	1.59	2.2
19.	2021	207.03	3.84	2.72	1.71	1.01	2.83
20.	2022	210.96	3.93	3.00	1.28	1.72	2.21

Source:-Office of Chief Registrar, Births & Deaths, Government of NCT Delhi.

*Revised as per latest population projection prepared by National Commission of Population from the Year 2011.

2.6 Post-2020 Studies: Migration in Delhi after COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic profoundly reshaped the discourse on migration in Delhi. The nationwide lockdown of March 2020 triggered one of the largest reverse migrations in India's history, with lakhs of workers leaving Delhi on foot or by makeshift *transport due to sudden job losses, lack of housing security, and absence of state support* (Srivastava, 2020). Images of migrant workers walking hundreds of kilometers became symbolic of the crisis.

Post-pandemic studies highlight several key findings. First, the *crisis exposed the invisibility of migrant workers in urban governance*. Despite their centrality to Delhi's economy, migrants were excluded from relief measures due to lack of ration cards, voter IDs, or domicile proof (Agarwal, 2021). Second, the *loss of income and housing insecurity disproportionately* affected women migrants, many of whom lost employment in domestic work and small factories (Banerjee, 2021). Third, the crisis accelerated debates on portability of social security and the need for a national migrant database (ILO, 2021).

Empirical studies conducted in Delhi post-2020 show that while many migrants have returned, their working conditions have worsened. *Wages remain depressed, job security is even more precarious, and debt dependence* has risen (Deshingkar, 2022). Moreover, housing vulnerability persists, with evictions resuming after temporary moratoriums ended.

Despite the visibility of migrants during COVID-19, Delhi's policy framework remains inadequate. Initiatives such as the e-coupon system for food distribution in 2020 temporarily addressed food insecurity, but long-term inclusion of migrants in welfare schemes is still limited (Rajan et al., 2021). The Delhi government's "Mukhya Mantri COVID-19 Pariwar Aarthik Sahayata Yojna" provided compensation to families of deceased breadwinners, but implementation gaps excluded many migrant households (Kundu, 2020).

Urban development under SDG 11 emphasizes inclusive and sustainable cities, but Delhi's experience highlights the challenges of aligning planning with migrant needs. The persistence of slums, inadequate housing, and weak labour rights undermine both migrants' welfare and sustainable urban development (Dupont, 2019).

2.7 Informal Labour Economy in India

The structural dominance of informal labour in India has been widely documented. Chen and Doane (2021) estimate that 92.4% of India's workforce remains informal, with significant variations across sectors. Construction, domestic work, transport, street vending, and small-scale manufacturing remain the primary sites of informality. Migrant workers dominate these occupations due to their availability for low-wage, flexible, and precarious work.

Scholars argue that the Indian state has historically "tolerated" informality as a mechanism of absorbing surplus rural labour without providing adequate social protection (Shah & Lerche,

2020). Employers benefit from low-cost, flexible labour, while the state avoids the fiscal burden of universal social security. The result is a labour regime in which migrants subsidize urban development through their precarious labour (Srivastava & Sutradhar, 2016).

Gender dimensions are central to this discourse. Women's participation in the informal sector is high, but their contributions remain undervalued and invisible. Studies highlight wage discrimination, lack of maternity protection, and vulnerability to harassment in domestic work, garment industries, and waste-picking (Banerjee, 2021). For migrant women in Delhi, these challenges are compounded by caste and class barriers, reinforcing cycles of marginalization.

Table 4: Data on Informal Labours in Organized and Unorganized Sector, 2017-2020

Type of Employment	Organized	Unorganized	Total
2017-18			
Formal	4.43	0.28	4.70
Informal	4.62	37.79	42.43
Total	9.05	38.07	47.13
2018-19			
Formal	4.91	0.45	5.35
Informal	4.55	38.87	43.43
Total	9.46	39.32	48.78
2019-20			
Formal	5.09	0.80	5.89
Informal	4.46	43.19	47.64
Total	9.55	43.99	53.53

Source : Economic Survey 2021-22 (Estimated using PLFS 2017-18 ,2018-19 and 2019-20 Surveys).

2.7.1 Informal Labour in Delhi

Delhi exemplifies the structural centrality of informal labour. Despite being a global megacity and India's capital, more than three-fourths of its workforce is informal (Kundu, 2020). Migrants form the backbone of this economy, concentrated in sectors such as construction, transport, small-scale manufacturing (garments, leather, plastics), domestic service, and street vending.

The *construction industry is one of the largest employers of migrant labour in Delhi*. Srivastava and Sutradhar (2016) document how construction workers, mostly seasonal migrants from Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and Jharkhand, live in temporary shelters at worksites, work without contracts, and face wage theft. The garment sector in East Delhi and unauthorized industrial areas similarly relies on migrant women and children, who work long hours for piece-rate wages (Priya et al., 2018). Street vending, another major site of informality, provides self-employment opportunities for migrants but is plagued by police harassment, lack of licenses, and frequent evictions (Bhan, 2016).

Housing and informality are closely linked. Migrant workers in Delhi's informal economy often reside in unauthorized colonies and slums near worksites, reinforcing spatial informality (Dupont, 2019). This dual informality—of work and housing—creates cycles of exclusion, where migrants remain invisible in labour statistics, urban planning, and welfare schemes. Following figure shows data on informal employment in India, Urban India and Urban Delhi.

Figure 4: Groups of workers in Informal employment by sex in India, Urban India, and Urban Delhi, 2022–23

Source: Created using the data of The 19th International Conference of Labour Statisticians data compiled with NSSO survey.

Despite its vulnerabilities, the informal economy contributes significantly to Delhi's growth. Migrant labour keeps urban services affordable, sustains construction and real estate development, and provides goods and services to the middle and upper classes (Bhagat, 2017). Informal workers also sustain rural livelihoods through remittances, linking Delhi's economy to source regions (Tumbe, 2018).

Some scholars argue that informality fosters innovation and resilience. Street vendors, waste pickers, and small artisans create flexible supply chains and low-cost services that adapt quickly to market demands (Chen, 2020). In Delhi, informal recycling networks managed by migrant workers play a critical role in waste management, yet they remain unrecognized by municipal authorities (Gupta & Mishra, 2019).

2.7.2 Vulnerabilities in the Informal Labour Economy

The vulnerabilities of informal workers are well documented. *Wage insecurity, lack of health and safety measures, absence of written contracts, and exclusion from social protection* dominate the literature (Srivastava, 2020). *Migrants are disproportionately vulnerable*, as their

lack of domicile documents excludes them from welfare schemes such as the Public Distribution System (Bhagat & Mohanty, 2019).

Delhi's governance structures often exacerbate informality. The Master Plan of Delhi prioritizes middle-class housing and infrastructure, while migrants are relegated to slums and unauthorized settlements (Bhan, 2016). Informal workers are frequently evicted in the name of city beautification, infrastructure expansion, or redevelopment projects (Dupont, 2019).

Policy frameworks such as the Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014, or the Building and Other Construction Workers' (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996, have limited impact due to weak implementation (Srivastava, 2020). Migrants often lack awareness of entitlements or face bureaucratic barriers to registration. This governance gap perpetuates informality rather than resolving it.

The COVID-19 pandemic dramatically exposed the fragility of the informal labour economy in Delhi. The lockdown in March 2020 halted construction, closed small workshops, and suspended domestic work, leaving millions of migrants unemployed overnight (Srivastava, 2020). Without savings or social protection, workers faced hunger, eviction, and forced return migration.

Post-pandemic studies highlight deepening precarity. Wages in construction and small industries fell, while working hours increased (Deshingkar, 2022). Women migrants, particularly in domestic work, faced job losses due to employers' fears of infection (Banerjee, 2021). Street vendors experienced severe income shocks due to mobility restrictions and loss of customers (Rajan et al., 2021).

The pandemic also intensified debt dependence. Migrants borrowed heavily from informal lenders to survive, deepening cycles of poverty. Housing vulnerability worsened as landlords evicted tenants unable to pay rent (Desai, 2021). These crises underscored the urgent need for inclusive policies, yet government relief measures remained inadequate, highlighting systemic exclusion of migrants from welfare.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study will adopt a *mixed-methods design combining quantitative and qualitative approaches*. This is appropriate because migration and informal labour are multi-dimensional, involving socio-economic, cultural, and political processes that cannot be fully captured through numbers alone. The quantitative study will include factors such as *demographic characteristics, economic status, occupational distribution, and educational levels*. *The qualitative aspect will capture migrants' lived experiences, challenges, agency, and coping strategies* within Delhi's informal economy.

3.2 Study Area

The research will be conducted in the National Capital Territory of Delhi (NCTD), which is one of India's largest recipients of rural-urban migration. Delhi's informal labour economy—including *construction, domestic work, street vending, small-scale manufacturing, and services*—makes it an ideal site to investigate migrant labour dynamics.

3.3 Sampling size and Strategy

A multi-stage purposive sampling method will be applied in three stages. In Stage 1 Selection of Settlements will be done such as slums, unauthorized colonies, and peri-urban clusters (e.g., Seelampur, Sangam Vihar, and East Delhi industrial areas) will be identified, as these are known migrant-dense localities. In Stage 2 household selection will be done within selected areas, households will be chosen systematically. Both male and female-headed households will be included to capture gender dimensions. In Stage 3 – occupational groups will be identified and representation will be ensured across construction workers, domestic workers, street vendors, garment/factory workers, and transport sector employees.

The sample size will consist of around 400–500 households (approx. 2000 individuals) will be surveyed quantitatively, supplemented with 40–50 in-depth interviews and 6–8 focus group discussions (FGDs) for qualitative insights.

4 DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Demographic Profile of the Sample

The study explores the socio-cultural adaptation and socio-economic profile of in-migrant labourers in the National Capital Territory of Delhi (NCTD), recognizing migration as a complex decision-making process shaped by multiple demographic and social factors. Variables such as age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, religion, caste affiliation, and language proficiency were investigated to assess how these influence both the causes and consequences of migration.

The demographic distribution reveals that the majority of migrant respondents belong to the economically active age groups of 20–39 years (71.9%), with an average age of 36 years, while household members are relatively younger with a mean of 24.4 years. This indicates that migration is largely driven by prime working-age adults, a trend consistent with findings by Deshingkar and Akter (2009), who argue that labor migration in India is predominantly undertaken by young adults seeking livelihood opportunities.

Educational attainment among migrants is notably low, with nearly 48.3% of respondents and 47.2% of household members being illiterate, and only a negligible proportion having studied beyond secondary school. This reflects the structural disadvantage of migrants, limiting their access to skilled employment. Similar findings are reported by Srivastava and Epari (2019), who

highlight that migrants in India's informal sector often come from low educational backgrounds, restricting occupational mobility.

The data also points to a male-dominated migration pattern (80.4% males vs. 14.6% females), reflecting the patriarchal norms that encourage men to migrate for work while women are often engaged in unpaid or care labor in their places of origin. This aligns with the ILO (2018) report, which shows that male dominance continues to characterize rural-to-urban migration in South Asia. However, within households, the gender balance is more even, suggesting that some degree of family migration occurs as well.

Table 5: Demographic Profile of Migrants

Background Profile	Profile of the respondents	Profile of the household members
Age in years (%)		
Below 10 years	NIL	22.8
10-19*	0.5	11.5
20-29	31.9	28.9
30-39	39.1	22.7
40-49	24.1	10.4
50-59	3.4	3.1
60 and above	1.07	0.6
Mean age	36.0	24.4
Educational Qualification (%)		
Illiterate	48.3	47.2
Studied upto primary	18.6	31.2
Studied upto secondary	24.2	17.5
Upto high school	1.9	5.2
Above high school	0.0	0.1
Non-Applicable cases ¹	---	6.0
Gender (%)		
Males	80.4	61.9
Females	14.6	43.1
Marital status (%)		
Married	86.9	59.4
Unmarried	2.2	37.9
Widowed	9.9	5.7
Separated	0	0.1
The religion of the Household Head (%)		
Hindu	95.0	95.0
Muslim	4.8	4.8
Christian	0.2	0.2
Caste/tribe of Household Head		

(%)		
SC	40.3	40.3
ST	3.0	3.0
OBC	52.9	52.9
General	3.8	3.8
Language known (%)		
Hindi	92.2	92.2
Others	7.8	7.8
Household belongs to Economically weaker section/BPL house		
Yes	50.6	50.6
No	49.4	49.4
Place of Origin (%)		
Rajasthan	10.8	---
Uttar Pradesh	43.9	---
Haryana	2.3	---
Bihar	29.8	---
Madhya Pradesh	13.0	---
Odisha	0.2	---
Duration of Stay in years (%)		
By birth	1.9	7.5
0.6-5.0	30.0	30.3
5.1-10.0	30.8	23.8
10.1-15.0	10.9	8.0
15.1-20.0	8.0	23.2
More than 20	18.4	7.2
Total	100.0	100.0
Total number of cases	650	2,056
¹ Non applicable are those cases in education which are not in the age of going to school *includes persons above 18 years of age who are considered as the head of the household		

Marital status shows that 86.9% of respondents are married, indicating that migration is not merely an individual strategy but also a household livelihood strategy. A large proportion of respondents belong to marginalized caste groups, with 40.3% Scheduled Castes and 52.9% OBCs, reflecting the over-representation of socially disadvantaged groups in the urban informal economy. Studies such as Kundu and Sarangi (2007) have similarly noted that migrants from socially and economically deprived groups dominate India's informal labor markets.

In terms of place of origin, most migrants come from Uttar Pradesh (43.9%) and Bihar (29.8%), followed by Madhya Pradesh and Rajasthan, states characterized by agrarian distress, high rural poverty, and limited industrialization. These findings are consistent with NSSO data and

corroborated by Bhagat (2017), which notes that UP and Bihar continue to be the largest sending states for rural-to-urban migrants. The duration of stay patterns reveal that nearly 61% of respondents have migrated within the last 10 years, while 18.4% have resided in the city for more than 20 years, indicating both circular migration and gradual processes of urban settlement

4.2 Reasons for Migration

Table 6: Reasons for Migration

Statements on factors responsible for migration (%)	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Improved employment prospects	2.0	14.0	84.0
The ease of finding employment	1.0	29.0	70.0
All family members' employment availability	9.0	28.0	63.0
Equitable pay distribution	6.0	55.0	39.0
Constant, routine labor	8.0	51.0	41.0
Payroll progress and ease of payment	52.0	34.0	15.0
Migration allows for more savings.	9.0	35.0	56.0
able to pay back debts at home	13.0	49.0	34.0
Understanding with employer	6.0	39.0	55.0
The workplace is free from prejudice.	12.0	47.0	41.0
A rise in the family's income	8.0	31.0	61.0
Capable of sending money home	23.0	30.0	47.0
Better prospects of education for children/family members	1.0	16.0	83.0
Simple opportunities to learn	4.0	33.0	62.0
Better opportunities for higher education accessibility	1.0	15.0	84.0
Improved medical facilities	0.0	12.0	88.0
Overall Improved facilities/infrastructure	0.0	14.0	86.0
Better public benefits	3.0	26.0	71.0
Over all economic improvement	7.0	42.0	51.0

Source: field survey

The reasons for migration highlight a combination of economic, social, and infrastructural push-pull factors. The most significant drivers include employment opportunities (84%), better access to education (83–84%), and healthcare (88%), alongside improved urban infrastructure (86%). This demonstrates that migration is not solely a survival strategy but also a pathway to upward mobility and better living standards. As Bhagat and Mohanty (2009) argue, access to urban amenities such as education and healthcare often serve as important pull factors in migration decisions.

From an economic perspective, 61% of respondents report an increase in family income, and 56% identify savings as a motivator, reflecting the importance of migration in poverty reduction and income diversification. Remittances also remain significant, with 47% acknowledging the ability to send money home, which supports findings by Stark and Bloom (1985), who emphasized remittances as a key household strategy in migration decisions. However, challenges persist: only 15% agree that timely wage payments are a motivating factor, while just 39% believe pay is equitable, indicating the precarious nature of employment in the informal sector. Srivastava (2020) similarly highlights irregular wages and lack of job security as defining features of India's migrant labor market.

Social aspects such as good employer relations (55%) and perceptions of reduced workplace discrimination (41%) suggest that migrants evaluate not only economic but also social working conditions when deciding to move. Furthermore, the aspiration for overall economic improvement (51%) underscores the dual push-pull dynamic, where poverty at origin and opportunities at destination intersect.

5 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary and conclusion

The study has tried to investigate the intricate relationship between migration and the informal labour economy in Delhi, situating the phenomenon within broader socio-economic and policy contexts. Migration emerges as both a survival strategy for rural households and a structural necessity for urban economies. The findings reveal that migrants in Delhi predominantly *originate from states such as Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan*, regions marked by *agrarian stagnation, rural poverty, and limited non-farm employment opportunities*. Migrants are drawn into Delhi's informal sector, which includes *construction work, domestic labour, street vending, rickshaw pulling, and small-scale manufacturing*. These occupations, while critical to sustaining the city's economy, remain undervalued, unregulated, and characterized by precarious employment conditions.

The demographic profile highlights that migrants are *largely young, of working age, and belong disproportionately to marginalized caste groups such as Scheduled Castes and Other Backward Classes*. *Educational attainment among them is very low, restricting access to formal employment* and reinforcing occupational vulnerability. Migration patterns are gendered, with men dominating *wage-earning roles in construction and transport*, while women are *concentrated in low-paid and insecure jobs such as domestic service and garment stitching*. This gendered segmentation not only reflects patriarchal labour hierarchies but also results in women migrants being more vulnerable to exploitation and exclusion from social protection.

The study underscores the paradox of Delhi's growth: while migrants form the invisible backbone of the city's informal economy, they are systematically excluded from urban planning,

welfare benefits, and labour rights frameworks. Basic entitlements such as subsidized food, housing, healthcare, and education often remain inaccessible due to domicile-linked eligibility criteria and administrative bottlenecks. The COVID-19 pandemic starkly illuminated these structural exclusions, with large-scale reverse migration exposing the fragility of migrant livelihoods and the absence of institutional safety nets. Many migrants faced loss of jobs, wage theft, hunger, and lack of transport, revealing their invisibility in the state's emergency response mechanisms.

The study also finds that migration is not a temporary or marginal phenomenon but a permanent and defining feature of India's urbanization. Migrants are essential contributors to Delhi's economy, yet their labour remains informalized, insecure, and undervalued. Unless migrants are recognized as integral to the urban social fabric and granted equal access to rights, entitlements, and protections, urban development will remain exclusionary and unsustainable. The study therefore emphasizes that inclusive urban growth and equitable labour markets require systematic recognition, integration, and empowerment of migrant workers.

5.2 Recommendations

The findings of this study make it evident that migrants are an integral part of Delhi's informal economy, yet they remain marginalized in policy frameworks and urban governance. To address these challenges, several policy recommendations emerge that can transform migration from a cycle of precarity into a pathway for inclusive development.

First, there is an urgent need for the *policy recognition and inclusion of migrants* within the ambit of urban planning. Migrants should not be treated as temporary outsiders but acknowledged as permanent contributors to the city's economy and culture. Urban development strategies such as the *Delhi Master Plan 2041* must embed migrant-specific provisions, including affordable housing, access to basic services, and inclusion in social welfare programs (Kundu & Sarangi, 2007). Recognition is the first step toward ensuring migrants' right to the city and their equal participation in urban growth.

Equally important is the *portability of social protection schemes*, given the mobile and circular nature of migration. While the *One Nation, One Ration Card* initiative has made some progress, its implementation must be strengthened to ensure that *migrant households can access subsidized food grains across states*. In addition, access to *healthcare, education, and pensions should not be contingent upon domicile or residence requirements*. As highlighted by the National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganised Sector (NCEUS, 2007), the portability of entitlements is critical to safeguarding the rights of migrants who contribute labour across state boundaries.

Strengthening *labour rights and protections* forms another cornerstone of the recommendations. Although legislation such as the Street Vendors Act (2014) and the Building and Other

Construction Workers Act (1996) exists, enforcement remains weak. Institutional mechanisms must be enhanced to curb *wage theft, enforce minimum wages, and ensure occupational safety*. Encouraging collective action through trade unions and self-help groups can also improve the bargaining power of migrants and reduce their vulnerability in highly informalized labour markets (WIEGO, 2018).

Given the *gendered nature of migration*, policies must adopt a gender-sensitive lens. Women migrants are disproportionately *concentrated in low-paying jobs such as domestic work and garment manufacturing*, exposing them to exploitation and lack of protections. Measures to ensure equal pay, prevention of workplace *harassment, provision of maternity benefits*, and access to affordable childcare facilities are urgently needed. Gender-responsive skill-development programs can further enable upward mobility for women, aligning with ILO's (2018) emphasis on integrating gender equity in labour markets.

Another pressing issue is the *housing and living conditions of migrants*, who often reside in unauthorized *colonies, rented rooms, or slum settlements with inadequate access to water, sanitation, and electricity*. In-situ slum rehabilitation and the development of affordable rental housing models should be prioritized to provide migrants with secure and dignified living conditions. Integrating migrant settlements into formal urban infrastructure will not only improve quality of life but also contribute to healthier and more sustainable cities (Bhagat & Mohanty, 2009).

The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the lack of preparedness for *crises affecting migrant workers*. To address this, a comprehensive migrant worker database should be developed at the national level to track mobility patterns and enable targeted interventions during emergencies. Institutionalizing emergency relief mechanisms—including provision of shelter, transport, food supplies, and direct cash transfers—would protect migrants from future shocks and ensure that they are not left invisible in policy responses (Srivastava, 2020).

Finally, the study emphasizes the importance of addressing the *structural causes of distress migration* in sending regions. States such as Uttar Pradesh and Bihar require sustained investments in rural livelihoods, agro-industrial development, healthcare, and education to reduce the compulsions that drive people into precarious migration. As the NCEUS (2007) report highlighted, tackling the root causes of migration in source areas is as critical as improving conditions in destination cities.

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